

Table 3. Information of SPPH in patients without antenatal PPH risk in different midwifery institutions

		secondary midwifery hospital (N=64)	Tertiary midwifery hospital (N=57)	P-value
Age (year)		32.4±4.4	32.3±4.3	
	<35	43(67.2)	40(70.2)	0.84
	35-39	19(29.7)	11(19.3)	0.21
	≥40	2(3.1)	6(10.5)	0.15
Gestational weeks		38.7±3.1	39.2±2.2	0.25
Hight (cm)		163.7±4.6	162.3±5.2	0.37
Parity	0	47(73.4)	44(77.2)	0.68
	1	15(23.4)	12(21.1)	0.83
	≥2	2(3.1)	1(1.8)	>0.99
Delivery mode	Vaginal	35(54.7)	31(54.4)	>0.99
	Caesarean	29(45.3)	26(45.6)	
Etiology	Tone	39(60.9)	34(59.6)	>0.99
	Tissue	6(9.4)	11(19.3)	0.19
	Trauma (%)	13(20.3)	9(15.8)	0.64
	Thrombin (%)	6(9.4)	3(5.3)	0.50
Results	Amount of bleeding (ml)	2282±1193	2201±1051	0.67
	< 2000	33(51.6)	27(47.4)	0.72
	2000-3999	22(34.4)	26(45.6)	0.26
	≥4000	9(14.1)	4(7.0)	0.25
	Max	5700	5000	
	Amount of Bleeding in vaginal delivery	2054±862	2222±1096	0.49
	< 2000	19(54.3)	12(38.7)	0.23
	2000-3999	15(42.9)	16(51.6)	0.62
	≥4000	1(2.9)	3(9.7)	0.33
	Amount of Bleeding in CS	2691±1464	2202±890	0.15
	< 2000	12(41.4)	15(57.7)	0.28
	2000-3999	9(31.0)	10(38.5)	0.58
	≥4000	8(27.6)	1(3.8)	0.03
	Admission to ICU	13(20.3)	23(40.4)	0.02
	PPH complications	32(50.0)	22(38.6)	0.27
	Coagulation disorders	27(42.2)	14(24.6)	0.05
	Shock	15(23.4)	13(22.8)	>0.99
	Kidney damage	4(6.3)	3(5.3)	>0.99
	Cardiopulmonary function disorders	4(6.3)	1(1.8)	0.37